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CORRELATE OF SOCIO-ECONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS INFLUENCING THE DURATION OF STAY OF IGBOMINA MIGRANTS IN LAGOS STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract: *Migration is a pivotal driver of socio-economic dynamics globally, yet effective integration remains a challenge particularly in urban hubs like Lagos, Nigeria. This research investigates the socio-economic factors that influence the length of stay of Igbomina migrants in Lagos, Nigeria. To achieve this, three Local Government Areas (Alimosho, Apapa and Kosofe) in Lagos State were used for the study. Simple random sampling technique was used to select 186 respondents from the list of registered members of Igbomina Association in the study area, for questionnaire administration. This constituted 10% of the registered members. In Addition, in-depth interview was also used to complement questionnaire administration. Data were collected on the socio-economic characteristics of the migrants, factors influencing their decision to migrate and factors influencing integration. Results show that increasing business opportunities (46%) and cultural affinity (34%) were the main factors attracting Igbomina migrants to Lagos. Multiple regression analysis unveiled that socio-economic attribute of Igbomina migrants significantly influenced their length of stay, accounting for 88% of variance at 0.05 level of significance. The findings underscore the pivotal role of socio-economic characteristics in shaping the duration of stay of migrants. Thus, this paper emphasised the need for robust integration strategies, and also advocates for comprehensive assimilation frameworks.*

Keywords: *Integration, Igbomina migrants, Lagos State, and Socio-economic Dynamics*

INTRODUCTION

Human mobility has remained consistent throughout history, and movement has been an important component of human existence in Africa and beyond (Barbosa et al. 2018; Nshimbi and Moyo 2020). Migrants' socioeconomic integration is critical to society since it provides economic and cultural benefits

while also helping to maintain social stability (Chen and Wang 2015; Zou and Deng 2022). In the dynamic landscape of urban centres like Lagos, Nigeria, the migration of diverse populations shapes not just demographics but also the socio-economic structure of these mega cities (Adagun 2021). However, in Nigeria the problems that are associated with

intra-movement are enormous (Adepoju 2008; Adesote 2017). This is because, in most circumstances, migrants who are not of the same tribe but of the same nationality or state of origin are regarded as foreigners and face integration difficulties (Odoemene 2008; Maliki et al. 2018). Migrants often face several challenges such as being segregated in residential areas, unequal job opportunities, disparities in school admissions, and difficulties in paying fees. These hurdles hinder their integration into society (Craig 2015; National Academies of Sciences, Medicine et al. 2016). In Igbomina land, which comprises of Irepodun, Ifelodun, Isin part of Oke-Ero Local Government Areas of Kwara state. This also includes Ila-Oragun, Oke -Ila and Ora Igbomina all in Osun State (Ibiloye 2017). This Igbomina migrants from these locations frequently search for fresh opportunities in Lagos State being Nigeria's primary economic centre (Ibiloye 2018). With an increasing number of Igbomina residing in various districts of Lagos State, It is critical to analyse the socio-economic factors influencing their duration of stay in these locations. In addition to the persistent need for Igbomina migrants to justify their right to enjoy privileges in the host community despite their long stay necessitate an in-depth analysis. Thus, the study aimed at assessing the correlate of socio-economic characteristics influencing the duration of stay of Igbomina migrants in Lagos State. The objectives of this study were to: (1) examine the socio-economic characteristics of Igbomina migrants residing in Lagos state, (2) examine the contributing factors that shaped the decision to integrate in host community and (3) determine the relationship between socio-economic characteristics and duration of Igbomina migrants' residency.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Migration signifies the relocation of individuals from one geographic area to

another, whether temporary or permanently (Adewale 2005). Migration is a major aspect of the nature of humans and it is an age-old strategy for human survival (Adepoju 2006; Nwosu et al. 2022). In general, migration has economic, demographic, and social consequences for both the place of origin and the place of destination (Reips and Buffardi 2012; Divisha 2017, McAreavey and Argent 2018; Eneasato and Anikwe 2020). This movement can be from rural to urban, rural to rural, urban to rural, urban to urban and across international boundaries (Idowu 2013). Migration from rural to urban areas is mostly influenced by societal strata affected by significant socioeconomic difficulties, with poverty being the most pressing challenge (Abbass 2012). This rural-urban transformation, fuelled by inequality, has impacted Nigeria's development policy (Agergaard et al. 2019; Sakketa 2023). Migration can intentionally promote redistributive development to control resource demand, availability, and associated population pressures by addressing gaps between rural and urban populations (Abbass 2012; Mustapha et al. 2015; Adeosun 2020).

Integration occurs in the public and private realms, across generations, and at the individual, family, community and national levels (Gropas 2021). According to (Martiniello 2006) Integration is a concept used to describe social, political, cultural and economic processes that occur when migrants arrive in a new society . He also observed that the process of integration does not take place at the same speed in the sphere of culture, politics, society and economy. Researchers measure integration in the host society through four dimensions: cultural, social, economic and political. These are the classical dimensions of integration, which in Boswell's terms gather all aspects of an immigrant's life (Messina and Lahav, 2006). The ordinary people often

express economic fears, such as worries about immigrants taking jobs from locally born citizens or being a burden on the welfare state, and so attitudes toward migration can become harsher in times of higher unemployment, even in countries that are otherwise relatively open to immigration (Palmer 1996; Banting and Soroka 2020). On the other hand, much opposition to migration centers on worries that migrants are too culturally and socially different from the host population, that they will fail to integrate, or that they will change the demographics and culture of a destination society too dramatically (Esses et al. 2003; Sniderman et al. 2004; Stephan et al. 2005; Citrin and Sides 2008; Hainmueller and Hopkins 2014; Citrin et al. 2022). An extreme version of these cultural anxieties is the “great replacement” conspiracy theory, postulating a deliberate attempt to make Whites extinct and replace them with non-Western immigrants (Obaidi et al. 2022). Of course, economic and cultural anxieties about immigrants are often tied together in people’s minds, and they can be mutually reinforcing.

However, it is equally clear that evidence of economic benefits is far from sufficient to generate public support for migration: the cultural and social dimensions must also be addressed (Esses 2021). To the extent that political fears stem from non-economic factors that is, concerns over social, demographic, and cultural change. There is a need to understand the sources of these anxieties in order to identify potential remedies. This paper makes a

plea to take the sociocultural dimensions of migration seriously. Migration policies that ignore people’s attachments to their society, culture, and politics will be ineffective, or even counterproductive.

The 2030 Agenda on Sustainable Development⁴ is an historic achievement that placed migration squarely on the global debate. The Agenda recognizes the positive contribution of migrants to sustainable development and expresses the need for international cooperation toward achieving safe, orderly and regular migration (target 10.7). Within the overarching objective of “leaving no one behind”, the Agenda calls for ensuring everyone’s equitable access, regardless of their migrant status, to health, education, decent work, legal identity (targets 10.2 and 16.9).

In addition, the Agenda contains a number of crosscutting issues that relate to integration and social cohesion and makes clear emphasis on the need to foster inclusiveness. The importance of cultural diversity, non-discrimination and violence prevention is highlighted (targets 4.7, 10.3, 16.7), as is the need to build capacities to promote non-discriminatory policies and laws (target 16.) (Guild and Grant, 2017). Integration is a cross-cutting and multi-sectoral issue that pertains to policy areas that address the economic, social, legal, cultural, and civic spheres and impacts all aspects of migrants’ lives and their communities (See Figure 1).

Figure 1: Element of Integration

Source: Guild and Grant, 2017

Between 1990 and 2000, the number of migrants in the world increased by 14 per cent, and the 175 million migrants in the world are projected to reach 230 million by 2050. Currently, 60 per cent of migrants live in the more developed regions, where migrants make up almost one in every 10 persons. However, there is a challenge of integration at the place of destination. In many societies, newcomers are often seen as outsiders who do not fit in (McAreavey, 2017). This perception of the "other" or "stranger" can be influenced by legal status, physical appearance, cultural differences, religious differences, class differences, or a combination of these things. These perceptions impact not just individual interactions, but also collective identities, forming boundaries between various social groups (Penninx and Garcés-Mascareñas, 2016). Migrants attempt to find their place in a new place in a variety of ways, including securing housing, work, education, and social and cultural adaptation. They want to be

recognised and included, especially if they feel distinct and are perceived as different by the host community (Penninx and Garcés-Mascareñas, 2016). Migrants integrate into societies in a variety of ways, depending on their historical, demographic, social, and political characteristics (Bloemraad et al. 2008; Rodríguez-García, 2010; Oyeniya, 2013). As a result, three possible approaches to community integration have been identified: assimilation, multiculturalism and exclusion (Faist, 2009; Rodríguez-García, 2010). Assimilation fosters equality by fully following the laws of the dominant society while ignoring variation. Multiculturalism, on the other hand, values and protects cultural diversity within a framework. Exclusion happens when ethnic-cultural communities become fragmented, frequently as a result of legal frameworks that restrict citizenship access (Rodríguez-García, 2010; Tecim and Yardım, 2016; Hong and Schmidt, 2021). In urban Lagos, Nigeria, understanding this phenomenon among Igbomina migrants is

crucial for fostering social cohesion. Investigating their socio-economic integration unveils the dynamics shaping community bonds and the collective fabric of urban life.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Lagos State is considered the most popular State in Nigeria and it is regarded as the commercial capital of the Country. It is located on Latitude $6^{\circ} 27^1N$ of the equator and longitude $3^{\circ}25^1E$ of the Greenwich meridian (Figure 2). In the last three decades Igbomina people have been moving in mass to Lagos for social and economic reasons. This research investigates the socio-economic factors that influence the length of stay of Igbomina migrants in Lagos, Nigeria. To achieve this, three local Government Areas (Alimosho, Apapa and Kosofe) were purposefully selected based on prior knowledge of Igbomina presence in the study area. A total of 186 copies of structured questionnaire were administered which translate to 10% of Igbomina migrants who are members of Igbomina Association in Alimosho, Kosefe

and Apapa which are 77, 65 and 44 members respectively. Based on prior knowledge the researcher also paid a reconnaise visit to the association meeting two months before the questionnaire were administered in the study area. This was necessary to be able to understand the terrain and characteristics of supposed respondents. Random sampling technique was used to administered questionnaire to respondents in each of the studied LGA. In- depth in-depth was also used to complement the questionnaire administration. The data collected were transform to measurable form using both parametric and non-parametric statistical tools such as multiple regression analysis, tables, percentages and charts. Multiple regression analysis was used to examine how length of stay of migrants is significantly influenced by the socio-economic characteristics of Igbomina migrants such factors such as age, gender, language competence, cultural practises, education, income, occupation, property ownership, inter-marriage, and business investments among Igbomina migrants were examined.

Figure 2: Lagos State, Nigeria showing the Study Area

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION
DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS
OF MIGRANTS

The result as shown in Table 1 reveals a significant disparity in the gender composition of migrants, with 60.2% male and 39.8% female. This statistical illustration depicts a significant gender imbalance in migratory trends within the research area. Such inequalities suggest that male migrants have a higher mobility rate, reflecting a greater

proclivity to relocate than their female counterparts. Previous research (Oyeniyi 2013, Hayfield, Aure et al. 2021, Zhao, Akbaritabar et al. 2023) have continuously highlighted male migrants' proclivity for long-distance and lengthy relocations. These findings highlight the gender-specific aspect of migration, demonstrating that males are more likely than females to engage in moves over bigger distances or for longer durations.

Table 1: Sex Composition of Migrants

Sex	Frequency	Percent
Male	112	60.2
Female	74	39.8
Total	186	100

Source: Author's fieldwork, 2020
Age Pattern of Respondents

Figure 3 shows a significant concentration of migrants aged 19 to 55, accounting for 80.3% of all respondents. This demographic profile reflects a large presence of the youth population among Igbomina migrants, emphasising their importance as the labour force's backbone due to economic activities at prime working years. The dominance of youth in migration aligns with existing literature, affirming the notion that young individuals exhibit a higher tendency to

migrate due to their energetic capabilities and aspirations for socioeconomic advancement (Hendrixson and Hartmann, 2019; Wyngaarden et al. 2023). This demographic trend also highlights the role of migration as a means for young people to seek better economic opportunities in other regions and contribute to their families through remittances (Naafs and Skelton, 2020). Additionally, the desire to financially support their families by sending remittances serves as a driving force behind their migration decisions.

Figure 3: Age Distribution of Respondents

EDUCATIONAL STATUS OF RESPONDENTS

Figure 4 depicts the educational composition of Igbomina migrants, revealing that 29.6% have completed primary school, 46.8% have completed secondary school, and 29.4% have completed tertiary education. Furthermore, a small percentage (3.2%) lacks formal schooling. The multicultural and multilingual nature of urban centres such as Lagos creates

an environment where linguistic proficiency, particularly in English or Pidgin English, is advantageous for business engagements. Consequently, migrants with a grasp of these languages are more likely to migrate to urban settings for economic opportunities, which influenced the higher prevalence of higher educational attainment among this group (Bhugra, 2004; Black et al. 2011).

Figure 4: Education Status of Respondents

LENGTH OF STAY

Figure 5 depicts how long migrants have stayed in the study area. Among the migrants, 25.8% have been in Lagos for 2-5 years, 8.6% for 6-10 years, and 12.4% for 11-15 years. Additionally, 29% have resided for 16-20 years, and 24.2% for over 20 years. This

implies that 65.6% of the migrants have resided in Lagos for more than a decade, suggesting their adaptability to the local culture and lifestyle. This extended stay has fostered a deep integration into the community, influencing their sense of belonging and families ties within the region.

Figure 5: Length of Stay

OWNERSHIP OF BUSINESS INVESTMENT AND LAND BY IGBOMINA MIGRANTS IN THE STUDY AREA

The study reveals that over seventy percent 74.3% of the migrants have their own business

investment in the study area, while 25.7% of them do not have business investment in the study area (Figure 6). Notably, the study reveals conditions in which migrants that have been in this town for more than a decade prefers to become proud business owners.

Figure 6: Ownership of Business

Furthermore, Figure 7 suggests that 42.2% of Igbomina migrants own land, while 57.8% do not. Acquiring land in Lagos State proves challenging for Igbomina migrants due to its demanding nature. Hence, most migrants secure land properties through community, family, or private channels. This limitation significantly impacts the majority of

respondents, depriving them of access to land for housing, security, business investments, and other socio-economic activities due to the inflated monetary value of land in the area. This barrier impedes their ability to fully engage in various aspects of socio-economic life within the community.

Figure 7: Land Ownership

BUSINESS ACTIVITIES AMONG IGBOMINA MIGRANTS IN THE AREA

Business activities significantly impact the integration and migration of individuals in and out of a community. Figure 8 illustrates that the majority of respondents work in distinct business sectors. Notably, 38.2% are involved in iron and steel commerce, while 29% sell building supplies. Furthermore, 17.2% are in the spare parts sector, and 11.3% are in the textile business. A lesser minority (4.3%)

engage in a variety of different business activities.

This result reveals that a significant majority of Igbomina migrants work predominantly in trade, particularly in Lagos' thriving building material business. This economic motivation drives their movement, underlining the region's economic prospects. The frequency of these specialised business activities among migrants highlights their economic significance and critical role in influencing migrants' assimilation into the local community.

Figure 8: Business Activities Engagement

FACTORS THAT INFLUENCED THE MIGRANTS' DECISION TO MIGRATE TO LAGOS STATE

The migration dynamics to Igbomina community, as depicted in Figure 9, delineate a multifaceted interplay of motives propelling individuals to relocate. These motivations are mostly the result of the interaction of pull and push factors, which include a variety of aspects such as socioeconomic drivers and host acceptability. The primary driver elucidated from the data highlights that an impressive 46% of migrants are driven to the region by increasing business opportunities, indicating a strong economic landscape within the region. This demonstrates the importance of economic opportunities as a magnet for migration, driving a considerable number of persons to seek better opportunities in the Igbomina community.

Furthermore, 34% of migrants cite cultural affinity as a compelling reason for their relocation. This highlights the significant influence of cultural ties and identity in shaping migration patterns, reflecting the intrinsic

importance of cultural ties in the decision-making process of persons choosing to migrate. In addition, the findings show that 11% of migrants attribute their relocation to the community's welcoming climate, indicating the significance of host acceptability as a factor promoting migration of Igbomina people to Lagos. Educational possibilities, accounted for 4% of the reasons given, and apprenticeship training, accounted for 5% of the reasons cited, as factors for migrating. Despite their lesser proportion, these factors highlight the importance of skill development and educational advancement as additional forces impacting migration patterns in the region. In short, this in-depth examination sheds light on the varied nature of migration to the Igbomina community, revealing the delicate interplay of economic, cultural, and social variables that motivate people to relocate. The dominance of business possibilities as a key driver emphasizes the critical role of economic opportunities in determining migration patterns, while simultaneously recognizing the importance of cultural and social links in this migration paradigm.

Figure 9: Reasons for Migration

EFFECTIVENESS OF EXISTING GOVERNMENT POLICY AND PROGRAMMES AIMED AT PROMOTING THE INTEGRATION OF MIGRANTS SPECIFICALLY FOCUSING ON IGBOMINA COMMUNITY IN LAGOS STATE

Lagos State is usually a home for all, according to people gazette (2022 report), it was revealed that Lagos state housed reasonable percentage of each of the ethnic tribes we have in Nigeria. Many of this tribe does have what we called segregation village. Thus, many people living in Lagos who are not even Lagosian usually enjoy the privileges that are associated with Lagos as a former Federal Capital Territory. According to Igbomina resident in Lagos, he maintained that, every year the Lagos State Government usually have meetings with all the home town associations through the senior special advisers and local government chairmen. The purpose of these meeting is to familiarize themselves with people who are not indigenes of Lagos State. He specifically asserted thus:

The only place where government cherishes migrant is Lagos. For instance, igbomina are distributed in about four Local governments area of Lagos state and I can tell you authoritatively that several Igbomina Indigenes have risen to certain top positions without any serious segregation which does not even happen in other states. /Vice Chairman/
Iron Rod Seller Union/Male/IDI) 26th June 2021/

Another migrant also added that:

In Lagos State, Government allows each tribe to have their leaders either as Hausa, Ibo, TIV, Igbomina etc. Once these tribes or ethnic

groups are through with their situation process, the Lagos ministry of Local Government Chieftaincy matter, do ratify their selection. In other state, it is the government that install individual whom they like and this breed some hatred /Igbomina migrant/male/IDI/24th June, 2021/

Another respondent also asserted thus:

Sometimes during Governor Ambode regime as a Governor, he abolished the use of separate school fees for indigene and non-indigenes. Through this, many non-indigenes were able to go to school. This is a good way to say the migrant are welcome in Lagos State. /Igbomina migrant/male/IDI/21th June 2021/

Relationship between Socio-economic Characteristics and Duration of Igbomina Migrants' Residency

The regression analysis in Table 2 shows a significant link between Igbomina migrants' length of stay and their socioeconomic characteristics ($R = 0.930$, $T = 27.090$, $p < 0.001$). This finding indicates that differences in socioeconomic characteristics have a major impact on the duration of migrants' residence in the destination area. The high positive correlation ($R = 0.930$) indicates that when migrants' socioeconomic attributes improve, their length of stay tends to rise. This association emphasises the importance of socioeconomic factors such as job prospects, income levels, access to education, and social integration in influencing migrants' decisions to stay in the destination region. The high coefficient of determination (R -square = 0.880, Adj. R -square = 0.877) suggests that the socioeconomic characteristics included in the regression model explain approximately 88% of the variation in the length of stay among

Igbomina migrants. This highlights the robustness of the model in capturing the influence of these factors on the duration of migrants' residence. However, there are still

issue of social segregation such as inability to contest for certain elective post, admission, into higher institution, land ownership or office ownership segregation.

Table 2: Regression Result of Length of Stay of Migrants and Socio-Economic Characteristics of Igbomina Migrants

Variables	B	Standard error of B	T	Sig T
Socio-economic Characteristic of Igbomina migrants.	.930	.034	27.090	.000
Constant	.881	.100	8.802	

Socio economic Variable	Individual Contribution (B)	Standard error of B	T	Sig T
Intermarriage Ownership of landed property	.050 .100	.034	27.090	.000
Ability to speak local language	.041			
Income	.092			
Ability to eat traditional food	.030			
Ownership of business	.130			
Investment				
Age	.170			
Gender	.140			
Education	.071			
Occupation	.110			
Constant	.881	.100	8.802	

Multiple R=.930; R. Square=.880 Adj. R-square=.877; standard error=.70193

CONCLUSION

This paper's extensive analysis has provided important insights into the factors impacting the length of stay among Igbomina migrants within Lagos State. The findings reveal that the level of integration encompasses various socio-economic variables such as monthly income, intermarriage, business and property ownership, linguistic proficiency, adherence to traditional practices, alongside demographic factors like age, gender, education, and occupation, collectively contribute significantly to the duration of migrants' residence. The diverse array of socio-economic variables indicates the multifaceted nature of migration decisions and settlement patterns among the Igbomina community. It is evident

that these factors, combined with individual characteristics, play pivotal roles in shaping the length of migrants' stay, highlighting the complexities of migration dynamics within the study area.

RECOMMENDATIONS

There should be an intentional effort by the host Government to create robust integration strategies such as giving a level playing ground in government policies. In addition to having an assimilation framework such that the offspring of migrants can be regarded as indigenes of their place of birth rather than the stigmatization of place of origin of their migrants parents.

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